

Well-being in the 'brain migration' studies

A scoping review protocol

Prepared for Registration to ZENODO

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CENTRE: Faculty of Political Sciences and Sociology
Doctoral Program: Political And Administration Sciences International Relations
Line of Research: International Relations: Dynamics of Change in the Global Society.

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Review title and timescale

1 Review title:	Scoping review about well-being in the 'brain migration' studies																			
2 Anticipated or actual start date:	21/05/2024																			
3 Anticipated completion date:	31/10/2024																			
4 Stage of review at time of this submission:	<p>This review has not yet started <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Review stage (Please check all that apply) Started Completed</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Preliminary searches</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Piloting of the study selection process</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data extraction</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Risk of bias (quality) assessment</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data analysis</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </table>		Preliminary searches	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Piloting of the study selection process	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Data extraction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Risk of bias (quality) assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Data analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Risk of bias (quality) assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
Data analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
Provide any other relevant information about the stage of the review here:	Not applicable																			

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10 Reviewteam members and their organizational affiliation			

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12 Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Review methods

13 Objective or review question(s):

(1) reviews with scope the research on the well-being of highly skilled migrants in search of constructs with which well-being is studied in brain migration and how studies on this topic can be classified.

14 Literature Search:

Comprehensive literature searches of electronic bibliographic databases Web of Science - Core Collection (WoSCC) and Scopus, selecting articles published in journals indexed in these databases, from a search vector on Brain Migration (Brain Drain, Brain Gain and Brain Circulation) and Well-being

15 URL to search strategy:

Search vector on Brain Migration (Brain Drain, Brain Gain and Brain Circulation) and Well-being in WoSCC: { TS=(((brain NEAR/0 drain) OR (brain NEAR/0 gain) OR (brain NEAR/0 circulation)) AND (well-being OR well-being)) }, and Scopus: { TITLE-ABS-KEY (((brain W/0 drain) OR (brain W/0 gain) OR (brain W/0 circulation)) AND ((well-being) OR (wellbeing))) }.

16 Condition or domain being studied:

The behavior of brain drainers (by definition, researchers/scientists and physicians/health personnel) and their migration flow is affected by perceived well-being (objective and subjective).

17 Participants/Population:

Physicians (including health professionals such as nurses), Researchers (including those studying to be researchers and researchers in training).

18 Intervention(s)/Exposure(s):

Application of questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, or participation in reflective processes about their work.

19 Comparator(s)/Control(s):

1) Focus on well-being of brain migrants, and 2) Research method, Migrant population analyzed, Sample (n).

20 Types of study to be included initially:

Publications then excluded letters, editorial materials, reviews, and documents containing only abstracts. Articles that were not related to the concepts of brain migration and well-being were excluded (this

process was repeated in the full document detail review). In addition, articles not written in English were excluded (other full-length documents written in German, French and Hungarian).

21 Context:

All periods of time and duration of follow-up are eligible.

22 Primary outcome(s):

There are two broad categories of outcomes that are of interest: 1) Theoretical constructs and items of construct on well-being of brain migrants. 2) Category of studies.

23 Secondary outcome(s):

Not applicable

24 Data extraction (selection and coding):

Using the *a priori* eligibility criteria, the data items in phase one correspond to 64 fields per record in WoSCC and 46 fields per record in Scopus, as detailed below. WoSCC: 1) Authors, 2) Book Authors, 3) Book Editors, 4) Book Group Authors, 5) Author Full Names, 6) Book Author Full Names, 7) Group Authors, 8) Article Title, 9) Source Title, 10) Book Series Title, 11) Language, 12) Document Type, 13) Conference Title, 14) Conference Date, 15) Conference Location, 16) Conference Sponsor, 17) Conference Host, 18) Author Keywords, 19) Keywords Plus, 20) Abstract, 21) Addresses, 22) Affiliations, 23) Reprint Addresses, 24) Email Addresses, 25) Researcher Ids, 26) ORCIDs, 27) Funding Orgs, 28) Funding Name Preferred, 29) Funding Text, 30) Cited Reference Count, 31) Times Cited, WoS Core, 32) Times Cited, All Databases, 33) 180 Day Usage Count, 34) Since 2013 Usage Count, 35) Publisher, 36) Publisher City, 37) Publisher Address, 38) ISSN, 39) eISSN, 40) ISBN, 41) Journal Abbreviation, 42) Journal ISO Abbreviation, 43) Publication Date, 44) Publication Year, 45) Volume, 46) Issue, 47) Special Issue, 48) Start Page, 49) End Page, 50) Article Number, 51) DOI, 52) DOI Link, 53) Book DOI, 54) Early Access Date, 55) Number of Pages, 56) WoS Categories, 57) Web of Science Index, 58) Research Areas, 59) IDS Number, 60) Pubmed Id, 61) Open Access Designations, 62) Date of Export, 63) UT (Unique WOS ID), and 64) Web of Science Record. And Scopus: 1) Authors, 2) Author full names, 3) Author(s) ID, 4) Title, 5) Year, 6) Source title, 7) Volume, 8) Issue, 9) Art. No., 10) Page start, 11) Page end, 12) Page count, 13) Cited by, 14) DOI, 15) Link, 16) Affiliations, 17) Authors with affiliations, 18) Abstract, 19) Author Keywords, 20) Index Keywords, 21) Molecular Sequence Numbers, 22) Chemicals/CAS, 23) Tradenames, 24) Manufacturers, 25) Funding Details, 26) Funding Texts, 27) References, 28) Correspondence Address, 29) Editors, 30) Publisher, 31) Sponsors, 32) Conference name, 33) Conference date, 34) Conference location, 35) Conference code, 36) ISSN, 37) ISBN, 38) CODEN, 39) PubMed ID, 40) Language of Original Document, 41) Abbreviated Source Title 42) Document Type, 43) Publication Stage, 44) Open Access, 45) Source, and 46) EID.

25 Risk of bias (quality) assessment:

Since this is a scoping review, we will conduct a risk of bias of the included studies will be assessed according to Campbell et al. (2014) in the case of theoretical articles and the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) scale will be used for quantitative, qualitative, and mixed studies (Hong et al., 2018). The MMAT scale is a valid measure of the methodological quality of the article. Two authors will review the studies independently, and a third author will be incorporated to settle tiebreakers.

26 Strategy for data synthesis:

The synthesis of results, we have used the method, the migrant population analyzed and the sample (including the alternative of not applying a sample) as comparative elements, contributing to the process of establishing study categories on brain migrants. As outcomes, we have focused on the constructs studied and the items that compose or disaggregate these constructs.

27 Analysis of subgroups or subsets:

Not applicable.

Review general information

28 Type of review

Select one of the following:

Review Type

Scoping review

Rapid review

Systematic review

Other: _____

29 Language

English

30 Country

Spain and Chile

31 Other registration details

Not applicable

32 Reference and/or URL for published protocol

Submitted to MethodsX – Elsevier for publication. Awaiting peer-reviewed feedback.

33 Dissemination plans:

Not applicable.

Do you intend to publish the review on completion?

Yes

No

34 Keywords

well-being, human mobility, high skill migrant, quality of life, social capital, socioeconomic status, social relationships

35 Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors.

Not applicable

36 Current review status

Ongoing (data cleaning phase)

37 Any additional information:

Not applicable

38 Details of final report/publication(s):

Note applicable (review still in progress)